

THE ISSUE OF PHONOLOGICAL INTERFERENCE IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract In the last decades the attention to teaching and learning foreign languages is increasing in Uzbekistan. Naturally, every language owes particular linguistic peculiarities. The phonological system of one language has distinctive features from another one. This phenomenon is a key contributor to the degree of the problem known as phonological interferences of language learners, since phonetic issues is considered as the basic matter to be acquired in language learning in order to have ability of the clear speech and perceiving target language correctly. This article aims to show some factor which impact on phonological interferences made by EFL students in the in the production of English sounds.

Keywords: English language teaching, phonological interference, English sounds, natural tendency, pronunciation, phonetic, language experience, phonology, vowel length, positive/negative transfer, phoneme.

INTRODUCTION

People from different parts of the world can be distinguished by their languages. When we confront a foreign language, our natural tendency is to hear it in terms of the sounds of our own language. We actually perceive it rather differently from the way native speakers do. Equally, when we speak a foreign language we tend to attempt to do so using the familiar sounds and sound patterns of our mother tongue. We make it sound, objectively, rather differently from how it sounds when spoken by native speakers. This is the well-documented phenomenon of phonological **interference**. The term "phonological" specifically refers to elements

that have a foreign accent, such as stress, rhythm, intonation, and speech sounds, which are transferred from one language to another. Interference is a term used in sociolinguistics and second language acquisition to describe the inaccuracy that a speaker brings into one language as a result of this contact with another language.

A number of scholars over the world have carried out researches on linguistic interferences. Scientist Odlin states that interference is also called language transfer or cross-linguistic influence, though these terms refer to a broader phenomenon and is often used interchangeably. Transfer suggests a practice in which some kinds of influence is essential for it to happen. In other words, one's native language influencing the language being studied is the result of transfer. Such influence may be positive when it facilitates the learning of skill by giving similarities between the two languages, or negative when a skill transferred from the L1 results in production that is different from the target language expectations.

According to Mahmud (2017, p. 57), Phonological interference may be mostly caused by borrowing system from another language. It is also called the interference of sounds if a speaker reproduces sounds of one language and make mistakes by adapting it with another language. Phonological interference mostly happens when the learners tend to substitute the particular target language sound with mother tongue phonemes when uttering one letter. It is because there are certain sounds of target language which do not exist in the mother tongue. Besides, the second language learners identify that target language as being the same as the mother tongue sounds which are actually different.

For gaining data on factors that influencing the students' phonological interference, a vast number of researchers conducted investigations and collected results were then transcribed and analyzed based on the theory of Piske, MacKay, & Flege. about factors affecting second language pronunciation. Piske stated that there are six factors that possibly influence second or foreign language pronunciation. The factors are described as follows:

- a) Age of Learning. Age plays an important role in second language learning. It is often claimed that a critical period (CP) exists for human speech learning. According to the critical period hypothesis, complete mastery of a second language is no longer possible if learning begins after the end of the critical period. Individuals who began learning an L2 before the end of the critical period for speech learning would have a much better pronunciation than individuals first exposed to the L2 after the end of the critical period.
- b) Gender. Most studies have identified gender as a significant predictor of degree of second language pronunciation. It gives significant influence on second language pronunciation ability. Females are usually assumed to have better pronunciation. However, many other studies suggested that the effect of gender may vary as a function of age of learner and amount of second language experience
- c) Formal Instruction Pronunciation as one of fundamental elements of English language has long been taught in formal instruction at school. Teachers are demanded to teach students English pronunciation to perform appropriate English communication skill.
- d) Motivation. Having a personal or professional goal for learning English can influence the need and desire for native-like pronunciation. Students can become highly proficient, even native-like speakers of second languages, especially if motivated to do so. Positive orientation to the language appears to be important factors in developing native-like pronunciation.
- e) Foreign Language Aptitude. Aptitude is related to auditory processing, such as phonemic coding. This in turn allows second language learners to hold more information regarding unfamiliar sounds, such as input processing, and makes it available for more detailed and refined linguistic analyses. According to Carroll and Sapon, as cited in Sadeghi and Khonbi (2015, p. 78), language learning aptitude is described as a complex of basic requisite abilities that make foreign language learning easier.

f) Language Use. Language use deals with how much second language learners spend their time speaking English at home or outside school. A high level of second language proficiency is much more likely to be maintained if the learners continue to use the second language frequently. Students who used English relatively often to have a significantly better pronunciation of English than students who used English relatively seldom.

Students' age of learning English as foreign language is influential to the students' English pronunciation ability. Scholar Hinkel cited that those who begin to be exposed to a second language after age 12 cannot ever pass themselves off as native speakers phonologically and cannot attain native-like levels of proficiency, even though according to Derwing and Munro (2014, p. 42), the acquisition of native-like accuracy is not really important to second language teachers as long as learners' speaking understandable. Further, Dunn (2011, pp. 1-3) argued that the best time to learn additional language is in young age because children are natural language acquirers who are self-motivated to pick up language without conscious learning. They have the ability to imitate pronunciation and work out the rules for themselves.

According to numerous researches, like the ones done by Rivera and Marisol, have been done on the effects of native language on second or foreign languages (2018,p. 33). They discovered that the two main ways in which Spanish pronunciation might be inferred phonologically in English were long vowels and consonant clusters. In English, a word's meaning can be altered by the length of a vowel, but not in Spanish. Additionally, pronunciation errors occurred because Spanish speakers read English using the same method (letter by letter) as they do in Spanish. The research result that Zheng conducted provides another discovery regarding native language interferences with second language acquisition (2018, pp. 1478-1484). He demonstrated that students in Northwest China struggled to distinguish between the sounds /n/ and /l/, /ei/ and /en/, and /u/ and /. All of these

were brought on by their inability to tell apart various Chinese phoneme pairs in their dialects. Furthermore, there were no long or short vowels in the dialect of central China, which caused confusion among learners regarding phonetic pairings. These phonetic pairs caused confusion among the students in this area: /n/ and /l/, /u/ and //, /i/ and /i/, /w/, /f/ and /v/, /f/ and /h/.

Researches conducted on analyzing the phonetic level of English in comparison with Uzbek show the followings: lack of English interdental sounds [θ] and [ð], which are often replaced by [d], [z] and [s], which can lead to confusion in words such as "think - sink", "thin - a sin - a tin". The English [r] is pronounced differently from Russian or Uzbek ones. In addition, English [v] is another difficult sound for Uzbek learners and it needs to be carefully distinguished from [b]. In the case of [v] the lower lip as active articulator, is pressed against the upper teeth in such a way as to allow the air expelled from the lungs to continue to pass through : in phonetic terminology, it is labiodental and fricative. With [b], on the other hand, the lower lip articulates with the upper lip and forms a firm contact with it such that the air flow is completely blocked for a moment: it is bilabial and plosive. Another phenomenon, vowel length, is also absent in Uzbek and Russian, but plays a great role in English. For example: to live [I] – to leave [i:], to book [U] - tooth [u:]. The famous phonetician Daniel Jones distinguishes two types of the letter "L" (dark and light) in English, which cannot be found in Uzbek.

Conclusion

Having been discussed the matter of phonological interference in language learning, it is proved that even though EFL students are often involved in English, their English pronunciation is still interfered by their native language because their engagement with English is merely through receptive skills (listening and reading), not through productive skill, particularly speaking or oral communication. To have good English pronunciation, what will help learners most is plenty of English conversation practice.

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